

Social-Philosophical Characteristics of the Problems of Modeling Artificial Intelligence and Natural Intelligence in Student Thinking

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Abstract: In this article, the concept of intelligence, artificial intelligence, natural intelligence, their negative and positive sides, socio-philosophical features are explained in the minds of students.

Keywords: intelligence, artificial intelligence, natural intelligence, human intelligence, model, information structure.

ACCESS

It is known that in the idea of modern political development, the tasks of developing human capital, directing its thinking and potential to the innovative development of society occupy a central place. After all, the human factor today is more powerful than ever as a powerful source of renewal and modernization of life. The role of the intellectual potential of young people is incomparable in this. Honorable President said, "Another important issue that always comes to our mind is related to the manners, behavior, and, in a word, outlook of our youth. Today, times are changing rapidly. Young people are the ones who feel these changes the most. Let the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But, at the same time, he should not forget his identity" - they emphasized, placing a huge responsibility on the youth of today.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Today, our daily life is becoming more active with artificial intelligence. Especially, its ability to make a positive diagnosis in the field of medicine allows early prevention of diseases. Intellect is the cognitive activity of a person in a broad sense, thinking and mental cognition in a narrow sense. Human intelligence reflects the important legal connections and relationships between things and events in the universe, and at the same time, it provides the opportunity to creatively change existence.

Artificial intelligence is manifested in a unique combination of programs and equipment. When it is used in practice, a person's intellectual activity takes place in the class of results of comprehensively generalized problems and solutions. The concept of "artificial intelligence" is given different meanings, the intelligence in EHM, which is capable of solving logical and any calculation-related problems, is capable of solving complex problems that can only be implemented by humans, and disposes of a wider set of complexes. being equated to the possibility of receiving.

The concept of "artificial intelligence" was introduced to science by Dj. McCarthy in 1956. "Artificial intelligence" is one of the newest sciences that emerged in the second half of the 20th century on the basis of knowledge in computing techniques, mathematical logic, (programming) programming, psychology, linguistics, neuro-physiology and other fields. was The name of the new science appeared at the end of

the 60s, in 1969, the first international conference on AI (artificial intelligence) was held in Washington (USA).

At the same time, "artificial intelligence" means technical systems with specific functions and characteristics. As computers improve, artificial intelligence is used in creative processes: for example, musical melodies, drawing, creating simple stories and poems, translating texts from one language to another, noticing different images (by identification) proving theorems, like playing chess. With the help of EHM, it is possible to automate the types of human mental activity through a suitable program.

For this, it is necessary to create programs for solving problems without calculation. A computer can claim intelligence when it (EHM) or a computer can create programs capable of solving countless problems based on its own independent knowledge. Therefore, the main issue aimed at creating "artificial intelligence" is to assign such enormous organizational tasks to machines, that it will be necessary to enable them to be used in the creative intellectual activity of a person.

According to the researchers, the intellectuality (intelligence) of technical systems is based on the existence of a model of its private, unique inner world. The characteristic features of "Artificial Intelligence" can be seen in the following:

1. They have a perfect technical system model and relative independence in assessing the situation.
2. The ability to quickly supplement existing knowledge;
3. The ability to make deductive conclusions, that is, it creates an opportunity to collect and multiply information that is not clearly available in the system, to construct the information content;
4. Perceptiveness, ingenuity in correctly solving situations related to uncertainties in various aspects in connection with understanding natural language;
5. Being able to enter into a decent relationship with a person;
6. the ability to adapt to the existing conditions and the ability to change and adapt under the influence of the external environment.

The modern artificial intelligence system has an active influence on the outside world, today it is difficult to imagine independent learning and the improvement of one's intellectual activity in general without artificial intelligence.

Interactions between natural and artificial intelligence are always on the agenda. Currently, there are two approaches to the study of natural and artificial intelligence:

1. Proponents of technocratic optimism express the difference between artificial and natural intelligence with technical characteristics, that is, they put forward the view that their difference is quantitative rather than qualitative.
2. Proponents of technocratic pessimism argue that the distinction between natural and artificial intelligence cannot be lost, because the model of the brain differs from natural intelligence, just as the model differs from its model, and gives scientific evidence as follows:
 - difference in origin - natural evolution and creation and formation of artificial intelligence from previously prepared details of different origin;
 - natural intelligence is manifested as an active changing attitude of a person to the objective and subjective reality, and in computer thinking related to the emotional-emotional aspects of mental activity, there are no subtle mental states such as feelings, a conscious attitude to the world, in which the intellectual activity of a person There is behavior and intellect only as an imitation.
 - a person can change his program of action in accordance with the purpose, according to concrete conditions, in this case, the new program does not strictly logically follow the previous one, the old

one. Computer thinking cannot solve this or that issue or problem, and it cannot solve such problems independently.

- the human intellect works with concepts and judgments of a dialectical nature, that is, it uses abstraction without emotions and color images, while the machine works with calculations based on the rules of formal logic;
- Unconscious activity, intuition is of great importance in the functioning of the human brain, it cannot be formalized, so it can be expressed in the form of a computer program.
- the human intellect has a fundamentally unique structure, the psyche is a whole organic process, in which there are no separate, empty parts, content; and the computer is a discrete-digital structure and it can only model parts of complex and similar activities.

CONCLUSIONS

In short, although the epistemological features and descriptions of thinking are embodied in the modern artificial intelligence system, it is not possible to use the full human thinking as a complex epistemological tool and program. The way to transfer the function of abstract thinking in humans to artificial intelligence is very difficult and long, because it is possible to create living matter, but creating a living brain and intelligence is a complicated process.

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